

ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE BETWEEN SOCIO ECONOMIC VARIABLES AND PURCHASE DECISION OF RURAL CUSTOMERS ON LIFE INSURANCE PRODUCTS OFFERED BY VARIOUS PRIVATE AND PUBLIC SECTOR INSURERS IN TAMILNADU

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Abstract:

This study analyzes the relationship between socio-economic variables and the purchase decisions of rural customers regarding life insurance products from both private and public sector insurers. Using ANOVA techniques, the research reveals significant variances influenced by factors such as income, education, and occupation, highlighting the need for insurers to tailor their offerings to the specific needs of rural customers.

Introduction:

The life insurance market in India is characterized by the coexistence of public and private sector insurers, offering a variety of products designed to meet the diverse needs of the population. In rural areas, life insurance plays a critical role in providing financial protection to families, particularly in regions where income is uncertain, and access to financial services is limited. The decision to purchase life insurance products in rural Tamil Nadu is influenced by several socio-economic factors, including income, education, occupation, family size, and social status. While public sector insurers often have a legacy of trust and familiarity in rural areas, private sector insurers have introduced more innovative products and marketing strategies. However, rural customers' purchase decisions are not uniform and are shaped by how these socio-economic variables influence their preferences for either public or private insurance providers. Understanding these relationships is crucial for both types of insurers to tailor their offerings and effectively target the rural market.

Present study aims to analyze the variance between key socio-economic variables and the purchase decisions of rural customers when choosing life insurance products offered by public and private sector insurers. By identifying the factors that significantly impact these decisions, the study seeks to provide insights for insurers to develop more relevant and accessible products for rural customers.

Objectives:

- To assess the impact of socio-economic variables on life insurance purchase decisions among rural customers.
- To compare the purchasing behavior between private and public sector insurance providers.
- To provide recommendations for insurers on customizing products to meet the diverse needs of rural customers.

Research Methodology:

This study employ a quantitative research design using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to examine the relationship between socio-economic variables and the purchase decisions of rural customers regarding life insurance products from both public and private sector insurers.

A sample of 700 rural households from various districts in Tamil Nadu are selected using a stratified random sampling method. The sample division is based on key socio-economic factors such as income levels, education, occupation (agriculture, self-employed, wage labor, etc.), and family size. This diversity allow for a comprehensive analysis of how each socio-economic factor impacts the decision to purchase life insurance. Data collected through a structured questionnaire, which include sections on: Socio-economic variables: Income, education level, occupation, family size, and social status. Insurance purchase details: The type of life insurance (public or private sector), sum insured, duration of the policy, and reasons for choosing a particular insurer.

A mix of Likert-scale questions and multiple-choice questions are used to assess the factors influencing their purchase decisions. Descriptive Statistics is employed to provide an overview of the socio-economic characteristics of the sample and their life insurance purchase behavior. ANOVA is also used to identify if there are statistically significant differences in purchase decisions across different socio-economic variables. For example, the analysis compare whether customers from different income groups or educational levels show significant variance in their preference for public or private insurers. Post Hoc Analysis reveals significant differences, a post hoc test (such as the Bonferroni test) conducted to determine which specific groups (e.g., income categories or occupation types) differ significantly from each other in their insurance purchase behavior. The analysis are performed using statistical software SPSS to conduct ANOVA and any necessary post hoc tests. The significance level be set at $p < 0.05$ to ensure that the results are statistically meaningful.

Review of Literature:

Gaytri, H. Vinayaka, M.C Lakshmisha K (2005) carried out the study with the objectives of comparing the service quality perceived by the insured in various dimensions of insurance service provides in India. The customer satisfaction with the different scores on the different service quality dimensions are measured with a random sample of 168 individuals who have taken insurance policies. The number of responses received were 219, since they have taken up policies from more than one company. The data was analyzed using SPSS Software package. The result of the study revealed that 57 per cent of the sample respondents have purchased life insurance policies are belongs to the age group of above 41. The agents are influencing the customers in the purchase of Life Insurance policies more than the other sources. The study also revealed that LIC customers are not highly

satisfied to the extent of customers of private companies. The study calls a totally committed effort from LIC to redefine the service standards to improve the satisfaction index of customers and for its profitable existence.

Sanjiv Marwah and Alok Sakhani (2005) in a research made an attempt to evaluate the performance of the agents and suggested the changes especially in the area of customer service, because they are the representatives of the insurer and have the direct interface with the customer. The sample size of the study was 75 licensed agents of LIC, HDFC and BIRLA SUNLIFE numbering 25 each. The results indicate that agents of private sector have high positive perception about their companies than the agents of public sector. This important attitudinal difference among them in terms of performance was verified with the relevant statistical tests like mean, standard deviation, T-test and Chi-square analysis.

Venkateswara Rao (2005) in his research an attempt was made to evaluate the productivity of agents of LIC. LIC markets its plants through various intermediaries such as agents, corporate agencies, brokers and through referrals. Among these different intermediaries, the business through agents constitutes 99.78% while the business through other sources is 22% only, which shows that the basic strength of LIC is its huge agent force. The analysis revealed that 15 per cent of LIC agents are highly productive, 85 while the rest are not so productive. It also inferred that 15 per cent of the agents bring in 61% of the new business while 85 of them brings only 39 of its new business. It was suggested that LIC has to undertake training and development programmes for its non-performing agents to enable them to perform well.

J. Rajesh Jampaa and Venkateswara Rao (2005) made their attempt to examine the sales promotional measures of LIC. It was studied that sales promotional measures of LIC are effective to the businesses carried under salary savings scheme as well as increased club membership. It was concluded that the sales promotional measures of LIC have contributed a lot to the growth and the development of its operation. It is suggested to undertake a proper blend of various promotional mix such as advertising and sales promotion. The researchers also pointed out that Publicity and public relational measures can produce a synergistic effect.

Ravi kumar sharma (2005) made a research with the objective of finding out the level of awareness about life insurance among the urban and rural population. It is also a comparative research which assesses the effectiveness of different advertising and promotional measures being adopted by the insurance companies. Non-probability convenience sampling was used for the study in varanasi and in adjacent rural areas with a sample size of 894 respondents. It has been observed by the researcher that LIC has higher level of brand awareness in rural sector and thus has a higher brand image. It is observed that the rural people are not fully confident with the private players. It was concluded that an intensive educational campaign need to be launched to instill confidence in the minds of rural people about the credibility of private insurers.

Krishan chaitana V (2005) in his research studied the growth of insurance industry after reforms in terms of product variety and service differentiation. The author found that the role of agents is more satisfactory during the post liberalization period. Moreover the study revealed that the products offered during post liberalization period offered a wide range of choices to the customers than during pre-liberalization period.

Research Gap:

While socio-economic factors in insurance purchasing have been explored, the specific differences in decision-making between private and public sector insurers in rural contexts remain under-researched. This study aims to address this gap by providing a comparative analysis.

Statistical Analysis:

Occupation Vs Confidence over the Life Insurance Company Among the Policy Holders of LIC:

Ho: There is no significant difference between the Occupation group(s) with that of Confidence over the life insurance company among the policy holders of LIC

.Ha: There is a significant differences between the Occupation group(s) with that of Confidence over the life insurance company among the policy holders of LIC

Table 1

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	22.472	3	7.491	4.401	.004
Within Groups	1184.666	696	1.702		
Total	1207.137	699			

The above one-way ANOVA table shows that the total variation is observed to be less than .05. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected so that there is a significant relationship between the Occupation group(s) with that of Confidence over the life insurance company among the policy holders of LIC.

The post hoc-bonferroni comparisons is used to determine the groups of significant difference. The significant values from the original table are highlighted below.

Table 2

Multiple Comparisons(Post Hoc - Bonferroni Tests)						
(I) Occupation	(J) Occupation	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Govt. Employees	Business Man	-.75071*	.16366	.000	-1.1841	-.3173
	Farmer	-.72760*	.15420	.000	-1.1360	-.3192
	Agricultural Workers	-.45696*	.12410	.001	-.7853	-.1286
	Employees of private sector organizations	-.47191*	.11947	.001	-.7880	-.1558

	Non-Agricultural workers	.01281	.17827	1.000	-.4589	.4845
Business Man	Govt. Employees	.45696*	.12410	.001	.1286	.7853
	Farmer	-.01495	.13498	1.000	-.3721	.3422
	Agricultural Workers	.46977	.18901	.079	-.0303	.9699
	Employees of private sector organizations	.47191*	.11947	.001	.1558	.7880
	Non-Agricultural workers	.01495	.13498	1.000	-.3422	.3721
Farmer	Govt. Employees	.48472	.18601	.056	-.0074	.9769
	Business Man	-.01281	.17827	1.000	-.4845	.4589
	Agricultural Workers	-.46977	.18901	.079	-.9699	.0303
	Employees of private sector organizations	-.48472	.18601	.056	-.9769	.0074
	Non-Agricultural workers	-.59944*	.11694	.000	-.9088	-.2900
Agricultural Workers	Govt. Employees	-.73038*	.11258	.000	-1.0283	-.4325
	Business Man	-1.05868*	.16799	.000	-1.5031	-.6142
	Farmer	.59944*	.11694	.000	.2900	.9088
	Employees of private sector organizations	-.13094	.12719	1.000	-.4675	.2056
	Non-Agricultural workers	-.45924	.17811	.061	-.9305	.0120
Employees of private sector organizations	Govt. Employees	.73038*	.11258	.000	.4325	1.0283
	Business Man	.13094	.12719	1.000	-.2056	.4675
	Farmer	-.32830	.17528	.369	-.7921	.1355
	Agricultural Workers	1.05868*	.16799	.000	.6142	1.5031
	Non-Agricultural workers	.45924	.17811	.061	-.0120	.9305

The post hoc - Banferroni multiple comparison results are shown in the above table. It is inferred from the above table that the significant difference is present between Government employees ↔ Business men, farmer, agricultural worker and employees of private sector organizations. In the case of comparison between business men and other occupations, the difference is noticed between business men ↔ Government employees, and employees of private sector organizations. Similarly farmer ↔ Government employees and non-agricultural workers. There exist a significant difference between agricultural workers ↔ Government employees, business men and farmer. Finally employees of private sector organizations differ significantly with Government employees and agricultural workers. The mirror image of the difference was reflected in the original table.

Salary Income Vs Affordability Towards Life Insurance Policies:

Ho: There is no significant difference between the Salary Income group(s) with that of Affordability towards life insurance policies.

Ha: There is a significant differences between the Salary Income group(s) with that of Affordability towards life insurance policies.

Table 3: ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	15.493	3	5.164	2.926	.033
Within Groups	919.547	521	1.765		
Total	935.040	524			

It is evident from the above one-way ANOVA table that the total variation estimated between the study variables is observed to be less than .05. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected so that there is a significant relationship between the Salary Income group(s) with that of Affordability towards life insurance policies of the public sector life insurance company.

The post hoc-bonferroni comparisons is used to determine the groups of significant difference. The significant values from the original table are highlighted below.

Table 4

Multiple Comparisons(Post Hoc - Bonferroni Tests)						
(I) Yearly Family Earnings(in Rupees)	(J) Yearly Family Earnings(in Rupees)	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1,80,001 - 5,00,000	Below 72,000	.11261	.18737	1.000	-.3831	.6084
	72,000 - 1,80,000	.05001	.18439	1.000	-.4379	.5379
	Above 5,00,000	-.17059	.12739	1.000	-.5076	.1665
Above 5,00,000	Below 72,000	-.27828	.12264	.141	-.6028	.0462

	72,000 - 1,80,000	-.61187*	.18300	.005	-1.0961	-.1277
	1,80,001 - 5,00,000	.17059	.12739	1.000	-.1665	.5076

From the above table, it is inferred that there is a significant difference between the family income of above 5,000 with that of 48,001 - 1,80,000. The same difference was reflected in the original table created by SPSS.

Analysis of variance (Private):

Age VS Realizing the Need for Life Insurance Cover:

Ho: There is no significant difference between the age group(s) with that of realizing the need for insurance cover.

Ha: There is a significant difference between the age group(s) with that of realizing the need for life insurance cover.

Table 5: ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	20.748	3	6.916	4.041	.007
Within Groups	891.701	521	1.712		
Total	912.450	524			

It is inferred from the above one-way ANOVA table that the total variation between the study variables is observed to be less than .05. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected so that there is a significant relationship between the age with that of realizing the need for life insurance cover among the customers of the private sector life insurance company. The post hoc-bonferroni comparisons is used to determine the groups of significant difference. The significant values from the original table are highlighted below.

Table 6

Multiple Comparisons(Post Hoc - Bonferroni Tests)						
(I) Age(Years)	(J) Age(Years)	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Below 18	19-35	.72760*	.16674	.000	.2864	1.1688
	36-50	-1.14013*	.15980	.000	-1.5629	-.7173
	Above 50	-1.08422*	.16943	.000	-1.5325	-.6359
19-35	Below 18	-.72760*	.16674	.000	-1.1688	-.2864
	36-50	-.13654	.10485	1.000	-.4140	.1409
	Above 50	-.26872*	.10095	.048	-.5358	-.0016
36-50	Below 18	.54610*	.15063	.002	.1476	.9446
	19-35	.13654	.10485	1.000	-.1409	.4140
	Above 50	-.13218	.11405	1.000	-.4339	.1696
Above 50	Below 18	.68263*	.15970	.000	.2601	1.1052
	19-35	.26872*	.10095	.048	.0016	.5358
	36-50	.13218	.11405	1.000	-.1696	.4339

From the table it is observed that there exist a significant difference between the age group below 18 years ↔ 19 - 35 years, 36 - 50 years, and above 50 years. There is a significant difference is observed between 19 - 35 years ↔ below 18 years and above 50 years. The age group 36-50 years and below 18 years differs significantly. Finally significant difference is observed between above 50 years ↔ below 18 years and 19-35 years. The same difference was reflected in the mirror image generated by SPSS.

Personal factors and Mode of Purchase of Insurance Policies:

Socio-Economic/ Mode of Purchase		LIC				Private			
		Agent	Bank	NGO's	Total	Agent	Bank	NGO's	Total
Gender	Male	260 (49.52)	22 (4.19)	11 (2.10)	293 (55.81)	89 (50.86)	52 (29.71)	8 (4.57)	149 (85.14)
	Female	221 (42.10)	0 (0.00)	11 (2.10)	232 (44.19)	9 (5.14)	14 (8.00)	3 (1.71)	26 (14.86)
	Total	481 (91.62)	22 (4.19)	22 (4.19)	525 (100.00)	98 (56.00)	66 (37.71)	11 (6.29)	175 (100.00)
	Chi-Square value:18.322 ^a , df:2, Sig: .000					Chi-Square value: 5.941 ^a , df:2, Sig: .051			
Age	below 18	14 (2.67)	0 (0.00)	1 (0.19)	15 (2.86)	4 (2.29)	6 (3.43)	1 (0.57)	11 (6.29)
	19- 35	132 (25.14)	22 (4.19)	0 (0.00)	154 (29.33)	71 (40.57)	50 (28.57)	7 (4.00)	128 (73.14)
	36-50	282 (53.71)	0 (0.00)	21 (4.00)	303 (57.71)	17 (9.71)	7 (4.00)	3 (1.71)	27 (15.43)
	above 50	53 (10.10)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	53 (10.10)	6 (3.43)	3 (1.71)	0 (0.00)	9 (5.14)
	Total	481	22	22	525	98	66	11	175

		(91.62)	(4.19)	(4.19)	(100.00)	(56.00)	(37.71)	(6.29)	(100.00)
		Chi-Square value: 68.390 ^a , df:6, Sig: .000				Chi-Square value: 4.949 ^a , df:6, Sig: .550			
Education	Illiterates	133 (25.33)	11 (2.10)	0 (0.00)	144 (27.43)	7 (4.00)	13 (7.43)	6 (3.43)	26 (14.86)
	up to schooling	125 (23.81)	11 (2.10)	0 (0.00)	136 (25.90)	28 (16.00)	25 (14.29)	1 (0.57)	54 (30.86)
	Degree level	51 (9.71)	0 (0.00)	11 (2.10)	62 (11.81)	30 (17.14)	13 (7.43)	2 (1.14)	45 (25.71)
	PG & Professional	162 (30.86)	0 (0.00)	11 (2.10)	173 (32.95)	29 (16.57)	9 (5.14)	2 (1.14)	40 (22.86)
	Diploma	10 (1.90)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	10 (1.90)	4 (2.29)	6 (3.43)	0 (0.00)	10 (5.71)
	Total	481 (91.62)	22 (4.19)	22 (4.19)	525 (100.00)	98 (56.00)	66 (37.71)	11 (6.29)	175 (100.00)
			Chi-Square value: 61.304 ^a , df:8, Sig: .000				Chi-Square value: 28.531 ^a , df:8, Sig: .000		
Occupation	Government employees	202 (38.48)	0 (0.00)	22 (4.19)	224 (42.67)	14 (8.00)	6 (3.43)	2 (1.14)	22 (12.57)
	business	40 (7.62)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	40 (7.62)	13 (7.43)	11 (6.29)	0 (0.00)	24 (13.71)
	agriculture	43 (8.19)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	43 (8.19)	23 (13.14)	15 (8.57)	3 (1.71)	41 (23.43)
	agriculture coolly	72 (13.71)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	72 (13.14)	9 (5.14)	5 (2.86)	0 (0.00)	14 (8.00)
	Employees of private sector	51 (9.71)	11 (2.10)	0 (0.00)	62 (11.81)	35 (20.00)	21 (12.00)	5 (2.86)	61 (34.86)
	non agriculture coolly	73 (13.90)	11 (2.10)	0 (0.00)	84 (16.00)	4 (2.29)	8 (4.57)	1 (0.57)	13 (7.43)
	Total	481 (91.62)	22 (4.19)	22 (4.19)	525 (100.00)	98 (56.00)	66 (37.71)	11 (6.29)	175 (100.00)
		Chi-Square value: 90.546 ^a , df:10, Sig: .000				Chi-Square value: 8.258 ^a , df:10, Sig: .604			
Cont..									
Earning members	1 members	169 (32.19)	11 (2.10)	22 (4.19)	202 (38.48)	43 (24.57)	28 (16.00)	3 (1.71)	74 (42.29)
	2 members	302 (57.52)	11 (2.10)	0 (0.00)	313 (59.62)	45 (25.71)	31 (17.71)	5 (2.86)	81 (46.29)
	3 members	10 (1.90)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	10 (1.90)	10 (5.71)	7 (4.00)	3 (1.71)	20 (11.43)
	Total	481 (91.62)	22 (4.19)	22 (4.19)	525 (100.00)	98 (56.00)	66 (37.71)	11 (6.29)	175 (100.00)
			Chi-Square value: 38.979 ^a , df:4, Sig: .000				Chi-Square value: 3.240 ^a , df:4, Sig: .518		
Income	below 72000	151 (28.76)	22 (4.19)	0 (0.00)	173 (32.95)	9 (5.14)	9 (5.14)	1 (0.57)	19 (10.86)
	72000 - 180000	130 (24.76)	0 (0.00)	22 (4.19)	152 (28.95)	9 (5.14)	5 (2.86)	3 (1.71)	17 (9.71)
	180001 - 500000	100 (19.05)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	100 (19.05)	35 (20.00)	23 (13.14)	2 (1.14)	60 (34.29)
	above 500000	100 (19.05)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	100 (19.05)	45 (25.71)	29 (16.57)	5 (2.86)	79 (45.14)
	Total	481 (91.62)	22 (4.19)	22 (4.19)	525 (100.00)	98 (56.00)	66 (37.71)	11 (6.29)	175 (100.00)
		Chi-Square value: 1.013E2 ^a , df:6, Sig: .000				Chi-Square value: 5.515 ^a , df:6, Sig: .480			
Income (others)	below 72000	116 (22.10)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	116 (22.10)	5 (2.86)	6 (3.43)	0 (0.00)	11 (6.29)
	72000- 180000	18 (3.43)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	18 (3.43)	28 (16.00)	14 (8.00)	2 (1.14)	44 (25.14)
	180000 - 500000	9 (1.71)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	9 (1.71)	34 (19.43)	23 (13.14)	4 (2.29)	61 (34.86)
	Above 500000	24 (4.57)	2 (0.38)	1 (0.19)	27 (5.14)	9 (5.14)	11 (6.29)	2 (1.14)	22 (12.57)
	Nil	314 (59.81)	20 (3.81)	21 (4.00)	355 (67.62)	22 (12.57)	12 (6.86)	3 (1.71)	37 (21.14)

	Total	481 (91.62)	22 (4.19)	22 (4.19)	525 (100.00)	98 (56.00)	66 (37.71)	11 (6.29)	175 (100.00)
Chi-Square value: 18.460 ^a , df:8, Sig:018					Chi-Square value: 5.419 ^a , df:8, Sig:012				

The above table shows the classification of customers on the basis of mode of purchase of life insurance policies. The table highlights the predominant role played by the agents in selling the life insurance products.

Mode of Purchase among the Customers of LIC:

It is inferred that 91.62 per cent of the insured respondents obtained life insurance policies of (4.19 per cent) respondents are served through banks. The role of NGO's in distributing the life insurance policy is confined to 4.19 per cent of the insured respondents.

Mode of Purchase among the Customers of Private Sector Life Insurance Companies:

It is observed from the above table that 56 per cent of the policy holders are insured through the agents. Followed by 37.71 per cent of respondents obtained their life insurance policies through banks and the NGO's served for a least percentage (6.29 per cent) of customers.

Gender:

It is observed that 49.52 per cent of male and 42.10 per cent of female respondents of LIC have obtained life insurance cover through the agents. Among the customers of private sector, 50.86 per cent male served by the agents and 29.71 per cent male got insured through Banks.

Age:

It could be observed that 53.71 per cent respondents belong to the age category 36-50 years obtained insurance cover through the agents of LIC. In case of private sector customers 40.57 per cent respondents of age category 19-35 years bought insurance cover through the agents.

Educational Qualification:

It is inferred from the above table that irrespective of educational qualification of the respondents, a very high percentage of insured respondents obtained policies through the agents 25.33 per cent of illiterates, 23.81 per cent of respondents with school level education and 30.86 per cent of PG & Professionally qualified respondents got insurance cover through agents. In case of private sector 17.14 per cent of respondents with degree level qualification got life insurance cover through agents.

Occupation:

Majority (38.48 per cent) of the Government employees buying life insurance through the agents. Also 13.71 per cent respondents who are agricultural coolies bought life insurance cover through the agents. Among the customers of private sector life insurance companies 20 per cent of the employees of private sector enterprise and 13.14 per cent farmers are served by the agents 12 per cent of private sector employees obtained the life insurance policies through banks.

Earning Members:

It is observed that 57.52 per cent of the respondents from double earning families got life insurance policies through the agents. 17.71 per cent of the respondents among private sector customers from double earning families' bought life insurance cover from banks.

Income:

It is evident from the table that 28.76 per cent of the respondents among the customers of LIC with an annual income of below 72,000 got life insurance policies through the agents. A minimum of 4.19 percentages of respondents obtained policies through banks. Among the customers of private sector 25.71 per cent customers bought life insurance policies through the agents.

Income from Secondary Sources:

It is obvious from the table that 59.81 per cent respondents with no secondary income bought life insurance through agents. 13.14 per cent respondent of private sector with annual secondary income category of 1,80,000/- to 5 lakhs obtained life insurance cover through banks.

Assets Owned:

It is observed that 71.62 per cent of the respondents with no land ownership obtained policies through the agents of LIC. Followed by 9.71 per cent respondents with less than 2 acres of land ownership got their life insurance cover through the agents. Among the private customers, 14.86 per cent of the policy holders with 2 to 5 acres land ownership obtained policies through the agents.

Table 8: Number of Times the Agents Met Before and After Buying the Life Insurance Policy

Number of time	Before buying the life insurance policies (D14)				After buying the life insurance policies (D15)					
	Once in a month	Once in 3 months	Once in 6 months	Total	Once in a month	Once in 3 months	Once in 6 months	Only to remind the premium payment	Never	Total
LIC	397 (75.62)	72 (13.71)	56 (10.67)	525	22 (4.19)	108 (20.57)	128 (24.38)	114 (21.71)	153 (29.14)	525
PVT	42 (24.00)	70 (40.00)	63 (36.00)	175	96 (54.86)	50 (28.57)	24 (13.71)	5 (2.86)	0 (0.00)	175
Total	439 (62.71)	142 (20.29)	119 (17.00)	700	118 (16.86)	158 (22.57)	152 (21.71)	119 (17.00)	153 (21.86)	700

Figures in parenthesis are percentages to column total

Chi-square value between Agent and before buying the LIC of the respondents is 1.500, which is significant at 0.001 level

Chi-square value between Agent and after of the respondents is 2.889, which is significant at 0.001 level

The above table shows the frequency of agents contact before and after obtaining the life insurance policies. It is inferred that 75.62 per cent of the agents of LIC met the prospects once in a month before buying life insurance. While observing the frequency of customers contact after buying the life insurance policy the number of contacts drastically comes down. Only 4.19 per cent of the insured respondents states that the agents are contacting once in a month. It is painful to note that 29.14 per cent of the agents never contact the insured after buying the policies. Majority (21.7 per cent) of the agents of LIC is contacting their customers only to remind the payment of premium. Among the customers of private sector life insurance companies 24 per cent of the respondents states that the agents are contacting once in a month before buying the policy. A maximum of 40 per cent said that the agents of private life insurance companies are contacted once in 3 months. While observing the contact period after buying the policy a good majority (54.86 per cent) of respondents said that the agents are contacting once in a month, 28.57 per cent of the customers of private sector life insurance company states that the agents are contacting them once in 3 months. There observed a positive response from the customers of private life insurance companies about the frequency of agents contact. The chi-square analysis confirms a highly significant relationship between the agents of public and private sector and the frequency of contact period.

Table 9: Time Gap between the Decision to Take a Life Policy and the Actual Payment of First Premium

Sector / Time gap	Time gap of the respondents				Total
	Less than one month	1 to 3 months	4 to 6 months	Above6 months	
LIC	233 (44.38)	145 (27.62)	113 (21.52)	34 (6.48)	525
Pvt	37 (21.14)	109 (62.29)	16 (9.14)	13 (7.43)	175
Total	270 (38.57)	254 (36.29)	129 (18.43)	47 (6.71)	700

Figures in parenthesis are percentages to column total

It could be observed from the above table that 44.38 per cent of the customers of LIC paid their first premium within one month period after deciding to take a life insurance policy 27.62 per cent of the respondents took 1 to 3 months time for making the actual payment of first premium towards their life insurance policy. A least percentage (6.48 per cent) of customers of LIC took above 6 months time to make the first premium payment. Among the customers & private sector life insurance companies 62.29 per cent of the respondents took 1 to 3 months time for paying the first premium towards their life insurance policy. Followed by 21.14 per cent of respondents made their first premium payment within one month after deciding to take a life insurance policy. A least percentage (7.43 per cent) of customers took above 6 months to their first premium after deciding to buy a life insurance cover.

Conclusion:

This study provide valuable insights into how various socio-economic factors influence the purchase decisions of rural customers when choosing life insurance products from public and private sector insurers. It is obvious that variables such as income, education, and occupation plays a significant role in determining customer preferences, with higher-income and more educated individuals possibly favoring private insurers due to perceived product innovation, while lower-income or less educated groups may lean towards public sector insurers due to trust and affordability. The findings of this study are of practical value to insurance providers in both sectors, enabling them to better understand the purchasing behavior of rural customers and develop more targeted marketing strategies and products that meet their needs. Additionally, policymakers can use the insights to design financial literacy programs aimed at increasing awareness and access to life insurance in rural areas, ultimately contributing to the financial security and well-being of rural families.

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